

ISic2951

I.Sicily inscription 2951

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.12.14 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance

South-West necropolis, epitymbion 508

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù, Museo Mandralisca

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108342

1. Πομπηία
2. Ρούφου Μέγα χάρε
3. Μέγα χάρε
- 4.

Edition: PHI332345

1. Πομπήϊα
2. Ροῦφου Μέγα
3. Μεγάλαι, χάρε.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284830

EDR 108342

EDCS 55702040

PHI 332345

Bibliography

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